

Is Public Debt Sustainable in Himachal Pradesh? Evidence from a Fiscal Reaction Function Approach

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the sustainability of public debt in Himachal Pradesh using a Fiscal Reaction Function (FRF). It evaluates whether the state government's primary balance is adjusted in response to changes in debt, using annual data for the period 2004-05 to 2023-24. The baseline model is estimated using ordinary least square (OLS) and is extended to incorporate macroeconomic conditions through output gap and structural shock through COVID-19 dummy variable. The results show a positive and statistically significant response of primary balance to lagged debt across model specifications, suggesting that fiscal policy has been responsive to rising debt levels. The inclusion of output gap and COVID-19 does not alter core relationship, rather it strengthens the evidence that fiscal behaviour is largely structural and not event driven. The study also examines debt stabilisation condition using interest rate – growth differentials and finds out that macroeconomics condition has been favourable for maintaining stable debt trajectory. There is no evidence of fiscal fatigue over the sample period. However, these findings are interpreted in the context of institutional support through the revenue deficit grant (RDG), which are no longer continued by Finance Commission. Overall, the result suggests that public debt in Himachal Pradesh has followed a broadly sustainable path during the study period, although maintaining this will depend on continued fiscal discipline and favourable macroeconomic conditions.

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I. INTRODUCTION

According to International Monetary Fund (IMF), A country's public debt is considered sustainable if the government is able to meet all its current and future payments obligations without exceptional financial assistance or going into default. Fiscal policy at the national level is increasingly evaluated based on debt sustainability in addition to deficit targets. The government of India has also set a target of 50% with 1% flexibility for its debt to GDP ratio, to be achieved till 2030. This shift from deficit-based targets to debt sustainability shows the growing relevance of debt dynamics in public finance.

Economists have a different view regarding public debt. Mercantilist Favoured the public debt whereas classical economists condemned due to lack of faith in role of government. David Ricardo characterises national debt as one of the most terrible scourges and David Hume consider that either the nation must destroy public credit or public credit will destroy the nation. Whereas the modern view

supports public debt due to its macroeconomic stabilisation capacity. Prof. A.H. Hansen, also known as the American Keynes, exponent of modern fiscal theory said that public debt is an essential means of increasing employment and has become an instrument of economic policy.

In the standard literature of public finance, government solvency requires that current debt should be backed by expected future primary surpluses. This condition was operationalised by Bohn (1998) through the fiscal reaction function (FRF) where primary balance (as ratio of GDP) responds to debt to GDP ratio, a positive and significant response is generally interpreted as evidence consistent with for fiscal sustainability. In public policy debates the growing debt to GSDP ratio is seen as a concern for sustainability, which finds support from macroeconomic models where taxation capacity is limited.

While this framework has been applied to advanced and developing economies, its relevance becomes particularly relevant in context of Indian states due to nature of fiscal

dynamics. Where most states are dependent on transfers from central government and have limited fiscal autonomy with constrained borrowing imposed through fiscal rules. These characteristics complicate the fiscal adjustment and raise question on whether subnational debt follow a sustainable path. Although debt is not always harmful as debt is useful for macroeconomic stabilisation (Blanchard,2023) as government spending has multiplier effect and support growth, but the high debt level with uncertainty is a point of concern. Therefore, the core question is, does the state government adjusts its fiscal stance when debt rises? If such response exists, then the debt remains sustainable and if not, fiscal stress tends to accumulate.

In this background the Himachal Pradesh is a relevant case. As a hilly state, Himachal is a tourism led economy with limited own revenue generating capacity, high committed expenditure, persistent fiscal deficits and high debt levels it exhibits characteristics of fiscal stress in the state. The state is continuously dependent on borrowing to finance its development needs and financial obligations. This creates an intergenerational burden of debt accumulation.

Himachal Pradesh historically has been receiving revenue deficit grant (RGD) by the Finance Commission. However, under the 16th Finance Commission such grants have not been continued in same form. This has led to fiscal adjustments including expenditure rationalisation which results as reduction in the state’s budget size (2026-27) and deferment of certain payments. These incidents raise a concern whether Himachal Pradesh’s fiscal behaviour is strong enough to compensate for withdrawal of institutional support.

Therefore, this study evaluates the debt sustainability of Himachal Pradesh by estimating a fiscal reaction function. The analysis begins with a baseline specification where primary balance is regressed on lagged debt. To capture potential non-linearity the quadratic specification is included. Further extension includes macroeconomic control variable such as output gap, reflecting role of business cycle and COVID-19 as a dummy variable to incorporate behaviour in corona pandemic.

The study is designed to capture the essential dynamics of fiscal adjustment. In addition to regression analysis the study also evaluates the debt stabilisation condition based on the interest rate and growth rate differential and assess whether the observed fiscal response is consistent with maintaining stable debt trajectory. The study contributes to state specific evidence by providing recent evidence from Himachal Pradesh.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II reviews the existing relevant literature on fiscal sustainability and subnational debt. Section III outlines the data and methodology which includes model specifications. Section IV presents the empirical results followed by

Section V as discussion and policy implications, and Section VI concludes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature in public debt sustainability has gradually shifted from accounting-based to more behaviour-based understanding of fiscal policy. A central concern is not just increasing debt levels but how the government responds to it. An empirical approach was developed by Bohn (1998), where he analysed whether U.S. government responds to debt accumulation through corrective action and finds out a positive response of primary surplus to debt level. Later in his work (2005), Bohn criticised earlier approach of Unit Root test for fiscal sustainability and strengthen his argument that fiscal reaction function can be a sufficient condition for sustainability under normal conditions.

The idea of non-linearity was introduced in the work of Ghosh et al. (2013). They introduced the concept of fiscal fatigue which means a weakening of response at high debt level. Their analysis showed that beyond a certain threshold governments are less able or willing to respond with high primary balance. This suggests fiscal response may get weak at high level of debt.

Different studies have supported the concept of fiscal fatigue. Study on Euro area shows that fiscal response weakens at the higher level of debt raising concern regarding effectiveness of fiscal adjustment within the monetary union (Checherita-Westphal et al., 2017). A similar result was seen in Latin America and Caribbean, where many countries exhibit a positive response but the strength weakens and is sensitive to macroeconomic conditions (González et al., 2023).

Blanchard (2023) in his book describe debt dynamics equation as change in debt depends on the interest rate and growth differential ($r-g$), debt and primary balance. He suggests that when $r < g$ government can sustain deficits without explosive debt paths provided condition prevails over time. Though this does not imply unlimited fiscal space due to uncertainty. He challenges the view of debt as harmful and emphasises that when $r < g$ economy may suffer from over accumulation of capital and under certain conditions public debt can enhance welfare and increase consumption in economy. Overall Blanchard supports the balanced fiscal approach that combines stabilisation objective with long term sustainability.

In the context of Indian states the issue becomes more complex due to subnational fiscal federalism. There is a vast difference among Indian states, due to weak revenue generation capacity and high expenditure in states like Punjab, West Bengal and Rajasthan faces unstable debt whereas Maharashtra and Gujarat maintain stable debt through fiscal management and there is a need for enhancing fiscal sustainability and debt management measures tailored to state specific economic conditions (Pavit,2025). In the

working paper by Shanmugam and Renjith (2022) they use the Bohn framework on 20 major Indian states and found a positive primary surplus response for only 4 states and further descriptive analysis shows that more than half of state’s debt is neither sustainable nor welfare enhancing.

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This section includes data sources, construction of variables and empirical framework used to analyse fiscal sustainability in Himachal Pradesh.

A. Data sources

To maintain consistency all the data are derived from Reserve Bank of India’s reports, which include Handbook of Statistics on Indian States and State Finance: A study of Budgets. The sample time period used for the study is 2005-06 to 2023-24. Further the Budget documents and Economic Survey of Himachal Pradesh is also referred.

The key variables used in analysis are:

1. Primary Balance: fiscal balance excluding interest payment i.e. Fiscal balance minus interest payment.
2. Debt: total outstanding liabilities of the state government.
3. Nominal GSDP: is the value of goods and services produced in the state at current prices and is used as a base for calculation of ratios.
4. Real GSDP: GSDP at constant price and has been used to calculate output gap, defined as deviation of actual output from potential output. Where potential output is estimated using the Hodrick-Prescott (HP) filter. A positive gap indicates economic expansion and negative gap indicates slowdown.

The fiscal variables are expressed in ₹ crore terms and converted into ratios using nominal GSDP as base to ensure comparability.

B. Construction of GSDP series

Due to change in base year of GSDP estimation, there was a challenge of structural break in time series data. To address this challenge splicing method is used to create an adjusted series with single base year.

Data on GSDP is available with 2004-05 and 2011-12 as a base year, so the former series is adjusted through forward splicing. Using overlapping GSDP data of three years, linking factor (LF_i) is calculated for each year and their mean is used as adjusted linking factor (LF_{adj}) for final calculation.

$$LF_i = \frac{GSDP_i (new\ series)}{GSDP_i (old\ series)}$$

$$LF_{adj} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 LF_i$$

Adjusted linking factor for real GSDP series is estimated as 1.743 and for nominal GSDP as 1.129 and old GSDP series is adjusted using formula:

$$GSDP_{adj} = LF_{adj} \times GSDP_{old}$$

The Final data set combines adjusted series (pre-2011) and original series (post-2011).

C. Construction of fiscal variables

The primary deficit is directly taken from RBI’s database and then converted into Primary balance by multiplying with minus sign. For analysis primary balance to GSDP (PB_t) and debt to GSDP (D_t) ratios is used where t denotes years.

$$PB_t = \frac{\text{primary balance}}{GSDP_n} \times 100$$

$$D_t = \frac{\text{debt}}{GSDP_n} \times 100$$

D. Output gap estimation

The study constructed an output gap series using Hodrick-Prescott (HP) filter in EViews software in following steps.

Figure 1: Output Gap

Source: Author’s calculation.

- Logarithmic transformation of real GSDP series, $Y_t = \ln (GSDP_{real})$
- the HP filter is applied to decompose Y_t into trend or potential output (y_t^*) and cyclical component (c_t), $Y_t = y_t^* + c_t$
- For annual data, smoothing parameter is set at $\lambda = 100$
- Output gap (actual – potential output) is calculated in percentage terms:

$$Y_t - y_t^* = c_t$$

$$Gap_t = c_t \times 100$$

This represents the percentage deviation of actual output from potential output.

E. Empirical model specifications

The analysis follows Bohn fiscal reaction framework where primary balance is regressed on lagged debt to analyse debt sustainability because fiscal policy reacts with delay, today’s primary balance depends on past debt. The following

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models are estimated to assess fiscal response under different specifications.

Model 1: Baseline Fiscal Reaction Function (FRF).

$$PB_t = \alpha + \beta D_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

A positive and significant β indicates that fiscal policy responds to rising debt which is consistent with sustainability condition.

Model 2: Cyclical adjustment

$$PB_t = \alpha + \beta D_{t-1} + \gamma Gap_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The output gap acts as a control variable for business cycle effect. It distinguishes structural fiscal response from cyclical fluctuations.

Model 3: Structural shock- corona pandemic

$$PB_t = \alpha + \beta D_{t-1} + \gamma Gap_t + \delta Covid_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where, $covid_t = 1$ for pandemic years, 2020–21 to 2021–22 and $covid_t = 0$ otherwise. This captures the fiscal effects during the COVID pandemic period.

Model 4: Non-linear specification

Quadratic specification is estimated to examine fiscal fatigue.

$$PB_t = \alpha + \beta_1 D_{t-1}^c + \beta_2 (D_{t-1}^c)^2 + \varepsilon_t$$

Where D^c is mean centered debt ratio used to reduce multicollinearity between linear and quadratic debt term.

$$D_{t-1}^c = D_{t-1} - \bar{D}$$

F. Debt dynamics framework

To complement the analysis, the study considers debt stabilisation condition.

$$D_t = \theta D_{t-1} - PB_t$$

$$\theta = \frac{1 + \bar{r}}{1 + \bar{g}}$$

Where \bar{r} is effective mean interest rate and \bar{g} refers to mean of nominal growth rate.

A $\theta < 1$ (i.e. $\bar{r} < \bar{g}$) indicates a favourable condition of debt stabilisation whereas $\theta > 1$ (i.e. $\bar{r} > \bar{g}$) indicates rising debt pressure. The interest rate (r) and nominal growth rate (g) is calculated as:

$$r = \frac{\text{interest payment}_t}{\text{debt}_{t-1}}$$

$$g = \frac{GSDP_t - GSDP_{t-1}}{GSDP_{t-1}}$$

All the models are estimated using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method using EViews software.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

In this section we present the empirical findings from fiscal reaction functions estimates. This part of study proceeds in

structured manner from baseline FRF model to incorporating cyclical and structural factors.

Figure 2: Debt to Nominal GSDP ratio.

Source: Author’s calculation.

Before presenting the regression results let us first examine the evolution of debt to GSDP ratio over sample period. In Fig. 2 the period 2004-05 to 2012-13 can be seen as declining phase of debt levels where it declines to 35% from 60%, after that the period 2013-14 to 2018-19 is a consolidation phase and debt level remains within 35-37% level. From the COVID-19 period debt ratio shows a gradual uptrend.

Table 1. presents the estimated result of fiscal reaction function across models followed by model summary.

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Constant	-5.72	-7.08	-9.08	-1.10
(c)	(2.18)	(2.23)	(2.35)	(0.48)
	[0.018]	[0.005]	[0.001]	[0.036]
	**	***	***	**
Debt_{t-1}	0.12	0.15	0.19	-
	(0.05)	(0.05)	(0.05)	
	[0.024]	[0.007]	[0.002]	
	**	***	***	
Output Gap	-	0.25	0.53	-
		(0.15)	(0.20)	
		[0.118]	[0.021]	
			**	
COVID Dummy	-	-	2.87	-
			(1.57)	
			[0.088]	*
D_{t-1}^c	-	-	-	0.03
				(0.06)
				[0.632]
(D_{t-1}^c)²	-	-	-	0.01
				(0.006)
				[0.053]
				*

Note:

- standard error in parentheses
- p-value in brackets
- *** p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.10

Model Summary

Statistic	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
R^2	0.26	0.37	0.48	0.42
Adjusted R^2	0.22	0.29	0.38	0.34
F-statistic	6.12	4.81	4.77	5.83
Prob (F-statistic)	0.024	0.023	0.015	0.012
observations	19	19	19	19

Source: Author’s calculation.

In the baseline regression model, the coefficient of lagged debt is positive and statistically significant at 5% significance level (p=0.024). This indicates that as debt ratio increases the government tends to improve its primary balance. This behaviour is consistent with Bohn sustainability condition. In the cyclical adjustment model, when we introduce output gap as a control variable for cyclical fluctuations, the coefficient of lagged debt improves and remains positive supporting baseline model and is statistically significant at 1% significance level. The output gap has a positive coefficient which is consistent with the theory, but statistical significance is relatively weak. This indicates that the fiscal response is robust to cyclical control and tend to improve during economic expansion, but the effect is not very strong.

The inclusion of COVID dummy does not alter the core findings. The coefficient of lagged debt again improves and remains statistically significant at 1%. The output gap shows improvement in significance level while COVID dummy itself is statistically marginal significant at 10% and indicate that pandemic affect fiscal aggregates, but it did not fundamentally alter the fiscal response. This implies that fiscal behaviour is structural rather than event driven. The overall explanatory power improves significantly with R-squared increasing to 0.48 compared to earlier specifications. To examine fiscal fatigue, quadratic specification is estimated using mean centered lagged debt ratio to reduce multicollinearity. The result does not provide support for non-linear fiscal behaviour. The linear term becomes statistically insignificant while quadratic term is weakly significant and its positive sign does not align with expected pattern of fiscal fatigue. There is no clear evidence for weak response at high debt levels. It should not be seen as an unlimited borrowing capacity. The result suggests a predominately linear relationship between debt and fiscal response. Although the result should be interpreted cautiously given the limited sample size. The findings do not support the hypothesis of diminishing fiscal efforts at higher debt levels.

For debt stabilisation condition, the value of estimated mean of effective interest rate (\bar{r}) is 0.0819 or 8.19% and mean of nominal growth rate (\bar{g}) is 0.1154 or 11.54%. Therefore, the value of theta (θ) is estimated as 0.9699 (i.e. 0.97).

As the mean of effective interest rate is less than mean of nominal growth rate ($\bar{r} < \bar{g}$) and theta is less than one ($\theta < 1$), this implies a favourable macroeconomic condition. Together with regression analysis it implies that debt is likely consistent with sustainable under current condition in sample period.

V. DISCUSSION AND POLICY IMPLICATION

The empirical results for the sample period 2004-05 to 2023-24 establish that fiscal policy in Himachal Pradesh responds positively to rising debt across specifications. In addition, interest growth differentials also point out towards stable debt condition.

Figure 3: Revenue Deficit Grant (RDG) as percentage of Nominal GSDP and a linear trendline.

Source: Author’s calculation.

However, an important aspect to consider here is that in sample period of study, Himachal Pradesh was receiving institutional support in the form of revenue deficit grant (RDG). As shown in Fig. 3, RDG has been a significant fiscal support to the state, averaging to 4-5% of nominal GSDP. With the discontinuation of RDG under the 16th Finance Commission, the external support is expected to be weakened. This shift signifies the role internal fiscal adjustment particularly in context of debt sustainability. While fiscal policy has shown positive response to rising debt in past, maintaining this behaviour becomes more important in the absence of external support.

The findings lead to several policy relevant implications. First, the positive response should be maintained through continued adherence to fiscal discipline and second, given the high level of committed expenditure, there is limited flexibility on expenditure side which indicate the need to enhance own revenue generating capacity. Third, maintaining favourable interest rate and growth rate differential by debt management and policies that support growth.

The borrowing should be done for productive expenditure that enhance long term growth potentials. Himachal Pradesh is a tourism led economy and spiritual and eco-tourism offers a significant opportunity of growth. At the same time there is a need to rationalise non-essential expenditures like unconditional cash transfers and untargeted subsidies, and to

manage long term liability of pensions and interest payments.

Given the state vulnerability to natural calamities and geographical constraint, building fiscal buffers at time of economic expansion should form integral part of fiscal policy. This will ensure that temporary shock does not convert to long term fiscal stress.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study examines the response of fiscal policy to evaluate the sustainability of public debt in Himachal Pradesh. Using fiscal reaction function the analysis provides evidence for behaviour of primary balance in relation to lagged debt, while accounting for macroeconomic condition and structural shocks. The empirical findings show the positive and statistically significant response of primary balance to increase in debt to GSDP ratio for the sample period. The result remains robust across models with inclusion of cyclical control and COVID related shock. According to Bohn’s framework the fiscal policy during the period 2004-05 to 2023-24 is not passive, rather consistent with requirement of long run debt sustainability.

The analysis also highlights the role of macroeconomic conditions. The estimated interest – growth differentials also indicate a supportive environment for debt stabilisation. This concludes that debt trajectory over the sample period is broadly sustainable. The findings point the importance of gradual improvement in fiscal balance rather than sharp consolidation. While there is absence of fiscal fatigue, this should not be interpreted as indication for unlimited borrowing capacity.

From a policy perspective, study suggest that maintaining sustainability will require a combination of continued fiscal responsiveness, improve revenue mobilisation and prudent expenditure management. Sustainability will depend on policies that support economic growth. In this context, sectors such as tourism offers potential to strengthen growth in hilly state like Himachal Pradesh. Strengthening the quality of public spending can further support the favourable interest – growth differentials.

The study does not explicitly analyse the quality and composition of spending of public debt, which remains an important area for future research. Deeper analysis of whether borrowing is for productive purpose, could provide additional insights for long term sustainability.

Overall, the evidence indicates a sustainable public debt trajectory in Himachal Pradesh for the sample period 2004-05 to 2023-24. However, sustainability in this context should be viewed as a dynamic outcome, one that depends on a continuous effort of fiscal response rather than a guaranteed state.

REFERENCES

1. Blanchard, O. (2023). Fiscal Policy under Low Interest Rates. In *The MIT Press eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/14858.001.0001>
2. Bohn, H. (1998). The behavior of U. S. public debt and deficits. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 113(3), 949–963. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355398555793>
3. Bohn, H. (2005). The sustainability of fiscal policy in the United States. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.708173>
4. Checherita-Westphal, C., Žďárek, V., & European Central Bank. (2017). Fiscal reaction function and fiscal fatigue: evidence for the euro area. In *ECB Working Paper Series* (No. 2036).
5. Ghosh, A. R., Kim, J. I., Mendoza, E. G., Ostry, J. D., & Qureshi, M. S. (2013). FISCAL FATIGUE, FISCAL SPACE AND DEBT SUSTAINABILITY IN ADVANCED ECONOMIES. *The Economic Journal*, 123(566), F4–F30. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23470568>
6. González, M. J., Hernández, J. M., World Bank, & Inter-American Development Bank. (2023). *Public debt sustainability and fiscal reaction functions in Latin America and the Caribbean* (IDB-DP-988).
7. Government of Himachal Pradesh. (2026) *Budget documents 2026-27*
8. Government of Himachal Pradesh. (2025) *Budget documents 2025-26*
9. Government of Himachal Pradesh. (2026) *Economic survey of Himachal Pradesh 2025-26*
10. Government of Himachal Pradesh. (2025) *Economic survey of Himachal Pradesh 2024-25*
11. Pavit. (2025). *Debt Sustainability in Indian States: A Fiscal R* analysis* (By Institute of Economic Growth). <https://www.ies.gov.in/pdfs/Pavit-march25.pdf>
12. Reserve Bank of India. (2025). *Handbook of statistics on Indian states*.
13. Reserve Bank of India. (2024). *Handbook of statistics on Indian states*.
14. Reserve Bank of India. (2026). *State finances: A study of budgets*.
15. Reserve Bank of India. (2021). *State finances: A study of budgets*.
16. Shanmugam, K. R., & Renjith, P. S. (2022). Empirical analysis on sustainability of public debt in Indian States. In Madras School of Economics & Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation, *MADRAS SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS*. <https://www.mse.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Working-Paper-235.pdf>